

On the Geothermal Potential of African Sedimentary Basins

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Figure 1: Overview figure BGS indicator analysis. BGS shapefile, maximum porosity indicator, combined indicator map, geothermal potential map, from left to right and up to down respectively.

1. Introduction

LEAP-RE & GAA

This project is conducted as part of the Long-term Europe-Africa Partnership for Renewable Energies (LEAP-RE). This new international partnership aims to create a long-term collaboration between European and African based private, governmental and academic institutions to help the developing countries of Africa to overcome the polluting transition that is associated with the development of a country. Additionally, this partnership is meant to stimulate the sharing of knowledge and promote innovation in the renewable energy sector. Currently, 83 institutions from 33 countries are involved in LEAP-RE.

As part of the LEAP-RE, the Geothermal Atlas of Africa (GAA) is introduced to identify potential geothermal exploration targets. The GAA consists of four components, the socio-economic part (W9.2), the engineering part (W9.3), the digitalization part (W9.4) and the geoscience part (W9.1). This project is part of the latter two parts. The end goal of the GAA is to create and maintain a digital interactive geothermal atlas of Africa, in which geothermal energy related information is presented.

Aims & Deliverables

The main aim and contribution of the project is to provide a first order assessment of geothermal potential in African sedimentary basins. More specifically, locate areas that appear to be suitable for low enthalpy geothermal energy exploitation and would warrant further exploration research. The low enthalpy systems are generally categorized by deep sedimentary aquifers that are heated passively by the heat of the earth. High enthalpy systems, where in addition to passive heat also heat from igneous processes is included, are not studied in detail for this project.

The deliverables of this project include a database in which all geological relevant information for geothermal energy exploration in Africa is compiled and digital geothermal potential maps that indicate areas where more in depth geothermal energy exploration could be beneficial. The database and the potential maps are based on geoscientific parameters and do not consider socio-economic or engineering related factors. In time, both the digital map and the database are to be incorporated in digital Geothermal Atlas of Africa (W9.4).

State of geothermal energy in Africa

Currently, the state of geothermal energy in Africa, on the continental scale is very inhomogeneous. Some countries including but not limited to Kenya, Tanzania, Algeria, Egypt, South-Africa (e.g. Kombe & Muguthu (2019), Lebbihiat et al. (2021), Dhansay et al. (2017), Lashin (2020)) have made significant progress in exploring geothermal potential in sedimentary basins inside their borders. However, the difference between the quality and extend of the exploration is large. Research and data on reservoir characteristics acquired by the hydrocarbon/petroleum industry can be used to identify sufficiently porous reservoirs that are important for geothermal exploration. Private hydrocarbon companies (e.g. BP, EXXON Mobil, Total Energies) have been producing from wells in Africa and therefore likely have (private) data on the reservoir potential of the petroleum systems they are exploiting. Furthermore, research on geothermal energy or reservoir potential is local and does rarely extend past borders.

Up till now, limited research on geothermal energy on the continental scale has been done. One of the exceptions to this is the work of Limberger et al. (2018). They assessed the geothermal potential for deep aquifers globally based on publicly available information by making calculated estimations on the different parameters that influence the geothermal potential (e.g. aquifer thickness/volume, temperature). However, it is important to note that the reservoir characteristics, as porosity permeability are generally assumed to be constant throughout the basin. Additionally, they assumed that the complete sedimentary thickness can be considered a permeable reservoir.

In this research we aim to use similar root data as Limberger et al. (2018), whilst distinguishing reservoir characteristics between and within the sedimentary basins of Africa.

2. Workflow for data compilation

Before establishing a workflow for producing digital geothermal potential maps, it is important to establish the type, quantity, extend and the quality of the data that is available. To this end, in the first part of the study, an extensive literature study was performed. This literature study includes data compiled by partners of the project in the GeoForschungsZentrum (GFZ) Potsdam online repository (managed by Anna Jentsch). The results of the literature study are presented in Chapter 3 and will be at the basis of establishing the indicator workflow in Chapter 4.

Literature study

The literature study mainly focuses on compiling geological data that directly provide information about the geothermal energy potential of systems. This information includes temperature related parameters (e.g. geothermal gradient, (surface) heat-flow) and reservoir related parameters (e.g. porosity, permeability, thickness). The literature study also focusses on data that indirectly could provide information about the geothermal potential. This information includes hydrocarbon related information (e.g. proven hydrocarbon reserves and provinces), sediment related information (e.g. sediment age, thickness and lithological and structural data). Additionally, basin related information such as basin nomenclature, geometry and basin onset age are also included in the data compilation part of the project. Basin nomenclature information proves essential in linking data between basins whereas basin geometry and location data is important in rooting reservoir data such as porosity in the spatial domain. The reasons for compiling these types of data will be further explained in the indicator analysis section of the report.

Establishing a GIS database

Most of the aforementioned types of data will be compiled so that they can be incorporated in a GIS based environment. These include shape files, (georeferenced) figures and Ascii grid files. Other data concerning reservoir characteristics, will be compiled in Excel in the format illustrated in Table 1. Note that porosity and permeability measurements will be averaged per type of measuring tool per article, which will be explained further in the indicator analysis part of the project. The Excel-database will also include an extensive hierarchal and synonym basin name list, which will be described further in the data availability section (Chapter 3). Hydrocarbon related information will also be included in the Excel-database.

Type of Data	Format	Unit	Description
(Sub) Basin Name	Name(s)	-	Name of basin or sub-basin
Direct Porosity	Max & Min Value	%	In case of AVG value, AVG = Max & Min
Porosity Type	Non-Differentiated, Effective (Neutron, Helium, Microscopy, Sonic, Core)	-	If type of porosity is not mentioned → Non-Differentiated
Direct Permeability	Max & Min Value	mD	In case of AVG value, AVG = Max & Min
Depth (range)	Top Fm – Bot Fm or Depth of Measurement	m	Can be AVG value. Can also be the depth range of measurements.
Fm Name/Sedi Age	Fm Name (Age) or Age (Lithology)	-	No Fm Name → Age & lithology. Fm name can be a group.
Type of Reservoir	Clastic/Carbonate/Mixed/Unconventional	-	No other options possible
Reservoir Thickness	Max & Min Value	m	In case of AVG value, AVG = Max & Min. Could be Net or Gross or complete Fm thickness
Figure(s)	(Local) Directory	-	Hyperlink (tables or parameter relationships)
Reference	Full Reference	-	Could include 2 if mentioned Reference is not accessible
Notes	Remarks	-	For example, remarks on Averaging

Table 1: Structure and description of reservoir characteristics database

3. Literature Study Results and Data Availability

The complete database (Including figures) and QGIS project are included in the report as Appendix A and B respectively.

Potsdam pre-compiled data

The GFZ Potsdam repository includes a variety of different data, ranging from papers and other meta data to shapefiles. Most noteworthy of which are the British Geological Survey (BGS) Trans-African Regional Geo-data for the Energy Transition (TARGET) model (Jones, 2022), data from the Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) (the Italian research council), the Earth model originating from the United-States Geological Survey (USGS) and the Nyberg & Howell (2015) basin model.

The BGS TARGET model, a GIS-based model (Figure 3, D), created by Darren Jones as part of the project, includes a variety of useful information from hydrocarbon well data, hot spring locations, heat-flow, lithological, lithosphere and structural fault data to most importantly a basin shapefile that indicates the location and some basic information about sedimentary basin in Africa with sedimentary thicknesses larger than two kilometres. The model also includes other socio-economic information which is of lesser relevance to us. The basin shapefile was created using literature and contains basin geometry, type, nomenclature and onset age information. This dataset is available in the public domain under the “Open Government Licence” which stipulates that this work is allowed to be freely if it is referenced accordingly.

The data from the CNR includes data on hydrocarbon exploration wells, planned and current geothermal wells, climate related data, groundwater data, seismic data, temperature and more. This data compiled by the CNR appears to originate from several different sources. Some of its contents will be covered in more depth later.

The Earth-model a digital GIS based geological map based on the geological map produced by the USGS (2001), that shows the age of outcropping rocks in Africa (Figure 2). It also includes information about population density and temperature in Africa. The non-GIS-based map originates from Persits et al. (1997).

Figure 2: GIS-based digital geological map of Africa, USGS (2001 (data from Persist et al. (1997))). Note that the colours are not according to the standard geological conventions.

The basin model by Nyberg & Howell (2015) is a GIS based map that predicts modern basin locations mainly based on topographic gradient and the presence of quaternary sediments. The basins are then classified based on basin type and climate zones. This basin model is not very useful for geothermal exploration as this model only indicates the current depocenters of sediment whilst ignoring older basin sediments that are generally more useful for geothermal energy exploration.

Other Shapefiles

After extensive literature study, four other noteworthy global/continental scale basin models were identified: from Evenick (2021), Robertson CGG (2019) (smaller company of the larger French multinational CGG), GETECH (2017) and the one from Selley and Van der Spuy (2016).

The model of Evenick (2021) (Figure 3, C) is GIS based model that aims to simplify basin geometry and nomenclature for future research. The model includes a large amount of basin data ranging from the basic (nomenclature, geometry, basin type) to more niche information such as sediment age, thickness and information on the presence of volcanic and the presence and age of evaporite rocks. This dataset is freely available for download from the ScienceDirect website. As the article is published by Elsevier, its terms of use apply here.

The model of Robertson CGG (2019) (Figure 3, B) is GIS based and includes, in addition to the basic basin information, also information about the status of hydrocarbon discoveries of a given basin. The model of GETECH (2017) (Figure 3, A) is GIS based and includes the basic basin information in addition to sediment age and thickness data. This model also contains synonym nomenclature information. Both these models can be downloaded from online viewers and are not allowed to be used without permission.

The model of Selley & Van der Spuy (2016) is not GIS-based and is composed of three figures that cover the NW, NE and southern part of Africa respectively (not shown). The model includes information about the geological age of the basins and shows the location of hydrocarbon fields.

Figure 3: The four main GIS-based basin models. A: GETECH (2017), B: Robertson CGG (2019), C: Evenick (2021), D: BGS, Jones (2022).

Additionally, GIS based hydrocarbon provinces and geologic provinces maps, created by the USGS for the world petroleum assessment program (Source of original maps: Persits et al. (1997)) are also included in the project. These shapes files only provide spatial information about the mentioned regions.

Important non-public datasets to note are the sediment thickness maps from the Exploration Fabric of Africa (EFA) and Getech, both of which are locked behind a paywall. Both maps show significantly higher resolution compared to the continent sediment thickness data from Laske & Masters (2013). The EFA also compiled other geological information in their database such as seismic cross-sections, basin geometry shapefiles, georeferenced publications from the American Association of Petroleum Geologists (AAPG) among other information.

The four main/comparable GIS-based basin shapefiles are shown in Figure 3 to show their differences and similarities. The colours represent the type of basin, yellow for foreland basins, the (dark) red colours for inter-cratonic sag basins, blue colours for rift basins, brown for orogenic related basins and cyan for the passive margins. Note the discrepancies in basin geometry and basin type between the different basin models. Despite this, the basin models generally shown similarities regarding the locations of specific basins.

Grids

Grids deemed important for the project include the temperature related grids from Limberger et al. (2018), the two most recent publicly available sedimentary thickness/depth to basement grids from

Laske & Masters (2013) and Straume et al. (2019). Additionally, grid-based information includes the National Oceanic and Atmosphere Administration (NOAA) National geophysical data centre, ETOPO1 Elevation model.

The most important temperature related grids from Limberger et al. (2018), include the annual global surface temperature and surface heat-flow grids. Additional grids include the global geothermal gradient grid, the temperature at depth grids and a several other geothermal potential related grids.

The highest resolution sediment thickness information for continents and oceans are the ones from Laske & Masters (2013) (From CRUST1.0) and Straume et al. (2019), respectively (Figure 4). The continent grid has a significantly lower resolution (grid size $\sim 111 \text{ km}^2$) compared to the oceanic grid ($\sim 10 \text{ km}^2$). The latter is compiled from different studies with the highest resolution whereas the former is an improvement from the global CRUST2.0 model.

Figure 4: Combined sediment thickness grids of Laske & Masters (2013) and Straume et al. (2019).

Excel database

The Excel database comprises different types of information. This information includes reservoir characteristics, lithological & seismic cross-sections, lithological and well column data (not complete/extensive), hydrocarbon systems presence information and basin nomenclature information.

As stated previously in Chapter 2, the reservoir characteristics data is structured as described in table 1 and individual porosity/permeability measurements are averaged per type of measuring tool per article. It is important to note that there is a large discrepancy between basins for data quantity, quality and type of information that is available. For example, Klett (2000) presents extensive tables with reservoir characteristics data for different reservoirs and different basins whereas Vicentelli et al. (2008) only mention one average value for the porosity of a vaguely specified reservoir in a basin. Additionally, not all basins that are identified in the literature have been studied extensively, resulting in the absence of reservoir characteristics data from these basins. Individual reservoir thickness data are also hard to compare directly to each other. For example, where Elsheikh et al. (2021) describes net reservoir thicknesses of about 15m with distinct net to gross ratios, other literature such as Ali (2015) only describes reservoir thicknesses as complete formation thickness. In total the reservoir characteristics database includes up to 451 unique entries for about 117 unique

basins. The visualization of the presence of at least 1 porosity measurement, projected on the BGS-basin model, is shown in Figure 5 (see figure description for legend). Note that this figure does not show any information regarding the quality of the porosity measurements. Projecting the data onto another basin model results in a different basin porosity availability distribution.

Figure 5: Porosity data availability projected onto the BGS basin model. Green, yellow and red colours indicate the availability of respectively direct, indirect (translated) and no porosity data, using the nomenclature link tables (described below).

The “cross-section” part of the database is composed of compiled figures of structural and seismic cross-sections of the different basins of Africa originating from the literature. Only cross-sections that are interpreted by the author are included in the database. The cross-sections that could be georeferenced in a GIS environment are shown in Figure 6. However, note that the cross-sections that could not be georeferenced are still included in the database. The cross-section shapefiles include fields that link to the figure (only available locally) and reference the origin of the figure. The quality difference between the different cross-sections varies significantly. For example, Wright et al. (2020), used a lot of seismic cross-sections from an extensive seismic study of Lake Tanganyika resulting in a high detail depth converted cross-section whereas other studies include not to scale schematic cross-sections with significantly less resolution and sometimes without units on the axes (e.g. Roberts et al. (2010)).

Figure 6: Map showing the georeferenced cross-section locations in blue. The information displayed on the right originates from the highlighted cross-section in red.

An incomplete section of the database is the “well and lithological column” section. This section includes some figures (and locations of some) of wells and lithological columns (of any kind). This section was discontinued due to limited added value the data could provide to the indicator analysis and because some wells were hard to verify if they were already included in one of the other shapefiles in the project. However, this type of information could be useful for future geothermal energy exploration and basin studies on the African continent and therefore by extension to the geothermal Atlas of Africa.

The hydrocarbon section of the database is compiled mainly from the Robertson CGG basin model, with the addition of a few other literature results. This section provides information on the status of a petroleum system of a given basin. It contains information on the exploration status of the basin, and it contains information on the hydrocarbon discoveries of a given basin.

Lastly, the database includes extensive nomenclature information on the sedimentary basins of Africa. This is important as the literature study shows inconsistencies regarding basin definition, geometry and nomenclature. The former two problems are best shown in the discrepancies between the different basin shapefiles (Figure 3). From the same figure, note that there is also no consensus about the basin type of the basins of Africa. Issues regarding nomenclature are especially apparent for basins located in two or more different countries. The same basin is known by the name “A” in country one but is known by name “B” in country two. An example of this is the Chad basin in Chad, which is known by the name “Bornu basin” in Nigeria (e.g. Adekoya et al. (2014)). Another nomenclature problem arises from the distinction between basin and sub-basin. For example, the Zaire and Sirte basin are well established in the literature. However, these basins could also be subdivided into smaller sub-basins with different names as illustrated by the BGS Basin model (Figure 3, D) (Jones, 2022). This conclusion is also in line with the conclusion from Evenick (2021). To solve/remedy this issue, the database includes extensive basin synonym and basin sub-basin link tables. Note that not all sub-basins mentioned in literature are included in this nomenclature list, as some sub-basins are too small to be relevant for this project specifically.

4. Indicator Analysis Workflow

Knowing the extent, quality and quantity of the data that is available allows us to formulate a workflow to assess the geothermal potential of the sedimentary basins of Africa.

From the results of the literature study, we can conclude that the available data is insufficient for a continental scale numerical analysis of all basins of Africa. However, for certain basins, particularly the larger ones in north Africa, it might be useful to perform numerical analysis to determine an estimate on geothermal potential in terms of energy/monetary value. Unfortunately, due to limited time, this opportunity remains unexplored for now.

Despite the inadequate data for some parts of Africa, an effort was made in this study to estimate the geothermal potential of sedimentary basins of Africa using direct and indirect indicators. These indicators can be used to provide an estimation on the feasibility of geothermal exploitation success of a given area. The chosen indicators for this project are the geothermal gradient, porosity (for clastic reservoirs), burial anomaly (for clastic reservoirs), basin geometry, sediment thickness, sediment age, hydrocarbon presence and sufficiently reservoir thickness. Each indicator will be discussed in more detail in the following sections.

Geothermal gradient

Temperature in the sub-surface is one of the most important parameters for geothermal energy. Locations with higher temperatures at depth are generally more favourable for geothermal energy exploitation than locations with lower temperatures at the same depth. This is because higher temperature at lower depths translate to a lower drilling cost as the borehole requires to be less deep. Such areas with anomalously high (or elevated) temperatures are characterised by high/steep geothermal gradients, i.e. the rate at which temperature increases per km depth. Geothermal gradients can be measured, for instance, in boreholes. However, here we will use the method of Limberger et al. (2018) to calculate the geothermal gradient from temperature at depth grids. The formula used in Limberger et al. (2018) is shown in Equation 1.

$$\text{Equation 1: } T(z) \approx T_0 + \frac{Q_0}{k} z$$

Where $T(z)$ is the temperature at depth (degrees Celsius), T_0 is the surface temperature (degrees Celsius), Q_0 is the surface heat-flow (W/m^2), k is the thermal conductivity ($W/m \cdot C^\circ$) and z is the depth (m). Note that we also adopt the $2 W/mC^\circ$ value that is used in Limberger et al. (2018). The geothermal gradient is then interpolated linearly between the temperatures at depths.

Shallower geothermal energy systems require less water to be pumped through the system and sustain smaller lithostatic overburden pressures. This generally reduces induced seismicity and costs. For these reasons we will use the indicator values as shown in Table 2.

Thermal gradient	Indicator Value
<15 C°/km	1
15-25 C°/km	2
25-35 C°/km	3
35-45 C°/km	4
>45 C°/km	5

Table 2: Thermal gradient indicator value distribution

Porosity as indicator for permeability

Permeability is a measure for how easily fluids can flow through a reservoir rock, which is very important for geothermal energy exploitation. The higher the permeability, the higher the production potential of geothermal energy of the system. Higher production rates in turn lead to an overall lower production cost of the system. Porosity can generally be used as indicator for permeability, as higher porosity generally results in higher permeability values. On one the most

common methods to determine matrix permeability from matrix porosity for clastic rocks (sandstones specifically) is the Carman-Kozeny equation (Equation 2; Carman, 1937).

$$\text{Equation 2: } K = S^2 * \frac{\theta^3 * D^2}{180(1-\theta)^2}$$

Where K is the single-phase permeability (m²), θ is the porosity (unitless), D is the average sand grain diameter (m) and S is the “Sphericity” of the sand grains which is 1 for a perfect sphere.

However, this relationship is less reliable for carbonate reservoirs for two key reasons. Firstly, carbonates are generally composed of more complex grain-shapes which makes them hard to describe as a bed of spheres. Secondly, carbonate reservoir rocks are less chemically stable than most clastic rocks. Processes as precipitation and dissolution can either or both change the overall porosity and permeability of a rock, making the porosity permeability overall more complex.

For these reasons, we only use porosity as indicator for permeability for clastic reservoir rocks and use the indicator values as shown below in Table 3. These indicator values are assigned to the maximum and minimum porosity measurements from the database. This way, these porosities and their associated indicator values are directly linked to basin names which can subsequently be projected onto the four GIS-based basin shapefiles.

Porosity (%)	Indicator Value
0-5	1
5-10	2
10-15	3
15-20	4
20<	5

Table 3: Porosity indicator value distribution

Burial anomaly

As established in the previous section, porosity is a key parameter for estimating the permeability of clastic reservoir rocks. However, a relationship that has not been discussed is the overall decrease in porosity with depth due to mechanical compaction. The relation between burial depth, porosity, bulk volume, density and compaction for sedimentary rocks are experimentally derived by Athy (1930). From his work, a relationship for how porosity changes with depth due to mechanical compaction was established (Equation 3).

$$\text{Equation 3: } \theta = \theta_0 * 0.01 * e^{-k_{athy} * (Z + Z_{burial}) * 0.001}$$

Where θ is the porosity at depth z (unitless), θ_0 is the surface porosity (unitless), k_{athy} is the porosity-depth decay factor for a given rock type (unitless), Z is the current depth (m) and Z_{burial} is the extra burial depth (m).

Important to note in this equation is the inclusion of the extra burial depth. This parameter indicates how much deeper the maximum burial depth is located from the current burial depth the sediment is located. The phenomenon of sediments being buried deeper in the past compared to now is called the burial anomaly. It is important to know how much this burial anomaly is if you want to infer or translate porosity data from one depth/location to another. For this reason, it is important to be able to estimate the amount of burial anomaly that took place at a given location.

One way of making this estimate is to compare direct porosity-depth measurements from the Excel database with the Athy equation as used in Limberger et al. (2017). For the depth of the measurement, the average between the maximum and minimum depth, as compiled in the database, is used. The remaining unknowns of surface porosity and depth factor are obtained from Hantschel and Kauerauf (2009). Here we compare our data to both a clay-rich and a clay-poor sandstone with values for surface porosity, 40 & 42 and Athy’s porosity-depth decay factor, 0.32 & 0.3, respectively. As we are comparing the data to sandstones, we only include data from reservoirs

which are identified to be clastic. This is a deliberate choice as in carbonate reservoirs porosity reduction is more complex compared to clastic reservoirs (Ehrenberg and Nadeau (2005)).

Before assigning indicators, we first calculate the percentual difference between the maximum and minimum data from the database and the two sandstone models. We then assign indicator values as shown in Table 4. Note that a lower indicator value indicates a larger burial anomaly. This method does not necessarily show us the true amount of burial anomaly, but it gives us a relative estimate. These indicator values are then directly linked to basin names which can subsequently be projected onto the four GIS-based basin shapefiles.

Percentual difference	Indicator Value
> 80%	+2
50% < x < 80%	+1
50% > x < -50%	0
-50% > x > -80%	-1
< -80%	-2

Table 4: Burial anomaly indicator value distribution

Basin geometry

Basin geometry is a more indirect indicator compared to porosity and geothermal gradient but can regardless be used to assess to some extent the geothermal potential of a location. Geothermal energy exploitation requires a permeable reservoir rock, generally a sedimentary rock. Most sedimentary rocks initially accumulates in sedimentary basins. Basement rocks to the contrary, are generally not very useful for geothermal energy exploitation due to their low porosity and permeability. The presence of a basin at a given location is thus more beneficial than the presence of basement rocks. However, as established in Chapter 3, there is no consensus on the exact location and geometry of the sedimentary basin of Africa. We thus propose that if multiple basin models indicate the presence of a basin at a given location there is a higher chance of there being a basin at this location. We therefore assign indicator values based on the amount of basin models that locate a basin at a given location (Table 5)

Amount of basin models	Indicator Value
0	0
1	1
2	2
3	3
4	4

Table 5: Basin geometry indicator value distribution

(Basin) sedimentary thickness

The sediment thickness of a basin (defined as the distance between the surface and the top of the basement) is inherently important for sediment being able to reach sufficiently high temperatures in the subsurface. This is because the temperature of sediment increases gradually with depth following the geothermal gradient. Therefore, a certain basin with a sedimentary thickness of one kilometre will have a lower maximum temperature compared to a basin with a sedimentary thickness of three kilometres. However, the porosity also reduces with depth due to mechanical compaction as explained in the burial anomaly section. This consequently means that basins with sedimentary thicknesses larger than three kilometres will also have lower porosities in their deepest sediments. For this reason, we decide to limit the highest indicator value at the three-kilometre thickness mark. The indicator values are shown in Table 6. For this we use a combined sedimentary thickness map of Laske & Masters (2013) and Straume et al. (2019). This combined map uses the highest resolution data for a given point. This essentially means Laske & Masters data for the continent and Straume et al. data

Thickness (km)	Indicator Value
0-1.0	1
1.0-2.0	2
2.0-3.0	3
>3	4

Table 6: Sedimentary thickness indicator value distribution

for the oceans and passive margins (Figure 4). Note that we use this combined sediment grid instead of a basin defined sediment thickness value, to be able to show lateral thickness variations within a basin. With this method, we include every location with a known sedimentary thickness and circumvent issues regarding basin definition.

Youngest sediment age

Sediment age can also be used as an indirect indicator for geothermal potential. This is under the assumption that the older the sediment, the higher the chance that processes have occurred that have negatively affected the matrix porosity. More specifically burial, compaction and other diagenetic processes. With this logic, younger sediments would be more suitable for geothermal exploitation. Here we assign indicator values as shown in Table 7 to the youngest sediments of a given location based on the (GIS-based) geological map of the USGS (2001) from the Earth model. We subsequently filter out all places with less than 500m sedimentary thickness. We do this to eliminate locations where these youngest sediments are only a small sedimentary cover for the basement rocks that are located underneath. Something to note, is that this method also excludes locations where young basins are formed. This is not problematic as sediments in young basins are unlikely to be of sufficient temperature for geothermal exploitation due to their shallow burial depth.

Age (Era's)	Indicator Value
Proterozoic & older	0
Paleozoic	1
Mesozoic	2
Cenozoic	3

Table 7: Sediment age indicator value distribution

Hydrocarbon presence

Geothermal exploration and hydrocarbon exploration show a fair number of similarities based on reservoir rocks. Both require sufficiently porous reservoir rocks through which fluids (oil, gas, water) can flow. Differences in the temperature aspect are that organic material has been subjected to higher temperatures in the past to form oil or gas and migrate into a reservoir rock, whereas geothermal systems require present day high reservoir temperatures.

Hydrocarbon presence	Indicator Value
Proven/part of province	2
Discoveries/potential	1
No data/disproven	0

Table 8: Hydrocarbon presence indicator value distribution

While the seal, source and migration parts of the hydrocarbon systems are not important to geothermal energy exploration, it is safe to assume that if a basin is host to a hydrocarbon system, geothermal energy exploitation is feasible. This is based on sufficiently porous and permeable reservoir characteristics. Do note that inversely the absence of a hydrocarbon system does not decrease the geothermal potential of a location. The data from the Robertson CGG (2017) basin model, data from the literature and data from the USGS hydrocarbon provinces are used to determine if a particular basin or location is host to or part of a hydrocarbon system. The hydrocarbon data from the database will be assigned indicator values as shown in Table 8.

Reservoir presence and sufficient thickness

And lastly, reservoirs require to be of sufficient thickness to be suitable for geothermal exploitation. The larger the reservoir thickness, the higher the geothermal energy production. This is due to the larger amount of volume of hot water that can be produced per unit of time. However, as mentioned before, the quality and type of reservoir thickness data varies significantly. This makes assigning meaningful indicator values, based on reservoir thickness only, difficult. We therefore choose to assign indicators to data entries that have either porosity or reservoir thickness data as evidence for the presence of a reservoir. If a reservoir has a thickness of more than or equal to 20m

and has a porosity of more than or equal to 10 percent, we assign a higher value to indicate that this specific reservoir is of sufficient quality. If there is mention of a (potential) reservoir but there is no porosity or reservoir thickness measurement a lower indicator value is assigned. This is shown in table 9.

Reservoir Presence	Indicator value
Reservoir thickness >= 20m & (phi >= 10%)	3
Reservoirs Data Available (phi or thickness)	2
Mentioned Reservoir but no explicit data	1
No Reservoir Mention	0

Table 9: Reservoir presence indicator value distribution

Calculation of the geothermal potential map

Before calculating the individual indicator maps, the direct data entries (the input data from the database in most cases) are filtered and checked for synonyms. The filtering is meant to reduce duplicates and only include the highest indicator value for a given basin (name). However, in the case of the porosity related indicators (porosity class and burial anomaly) both the highest indicator and the lowest indicator values are included. The result is a reduced excel form with only direct data.

From this direct data, we use the nomenclature link tables to be able to translate direct data entries for one basin to a comparable, in terms of formation history and sedimentary and tectonic processes, neighbouring basin. If a direct basin entry is a main basin, all associated sub-basins (as established in nomenclature link tables) will also receive an indirect basin data entry.

Both the direct entries and the indirect entries are then combined in a combined excel input-file which subsequently is used to project the data onto the four basin models. Note, that if a basin has both indirect and direct entries, the highest indicator value will be used.

The reason for including the highest indicator value is because if for example a basin has multiple potential reservoirs, it would be sensible to choose to exploit the reservoir that has the highest potential. The reason for also including the lowest potential porosity indicators is to show the variability in porosity measurements from the literature. This makes sense as the compilation of porosity in this type of analysis is the main contribution to science and this project as a whole.

After creating all individual indicator maps, the indicator values are added together in one larger indicator map. As result of the choosing to include both minimum and maximum porosity in addition to compare porosity-depth relation to both clay rich as clay poor sandstone, eight maps are created for each basin model. The names relate to the combination of the chosen indicator maps. The names are composed of: “[basin model name]_[maximum or minimum porosity indicator]_[Clay rich (cr) or clay poor (cp) burial anomaly curve]_[minimum or maximum burial anomaly indicator]”.

This way, a given location, is assigned an indicator value ranging from 1 to 28. These values are then translated to geothermal potential using the indicator value ranges as shown in Table 10.

Geothermal potential	Indicator value range
Not Favourable	1 >= x > 6
Slightly Favourable	6 >= x > 12
Favourable	12 >= x > 18
Very Favourable	X > 18

Table 10: Geothermal potential verdict ranges

5. Results indicator analysis

The complete Python code as PyCharm project used for the analysis is included in the report as Appendix C. Appendix D includes all the input and output files of the analysis (Excel). The individual indicator maps are shown in Appendix E. Some representative results of the final indicator maps and geothermal potential maps are shown below in Figures 11-14 and Figures 15-18 respectively. The remaining Indicator and geothermal potential figures (including the Ascii files) are included in Appendix F and G respectively.

Porosity and burial anomaly

Figure 7 shows the distribution of all porosity measurements with associated depth information from the Excel database in a porosity depth curve. The green and blue dots indicate the minimum and maximum porosity measurements respectively. The continuous yellow and orange curves indicate the porosity-depth relationship of clay poor and clay rich sandstone respectively, according to the mechanical compaction equation of Athy (1930) (Equation 2). The two types of dashed lines indicate the $\pm 50\%$ and $\pm 80\%$ deviation from the porosity depth curve respectively. We observe that most of the minimum porosity data are deviating significantly from the mechanical compaction porosity-depth curve. These points are show generally significantly lower porosities compared to the porosity depth curves. Whereas the maximum porosity data generally plot close to the porosity depth curves, except for a few data points that show significantly higher porosities than the porosity-depth curves.

Figure 7: Porosity-depth data and mechanical compaction models for clay poor and clay rich sandstone, Athy (1930)

Indicator maps

Figures 8 and 9-10 show the basin model independent and the BGS related indicator maps. The other basin model related indicator maps are shown in Appendix E. The geothermal gradient indicator map (Figure 8, upper left) shows two areas where the geothermal gradient is the highest. These areas are the north-western part of Africa (Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia and the Atlas Mountains) and the mid-eastern part of Africa towards the south-western part of Africa (from Ethiopia to Namibia, as part of the east-African rift zone). The area in between (from Egypt to Senegal and Gabon) is characterized by significantly lower geothermal gradients.

The sedimentary age indicator map (Figure 8, upper right) shows that most of the basins are relatively young. Exceptions include the Karoo basin in South-Africa, the Volta basin in Ghana, the Bové basin in Guinea and smaller areas between the larger basin of north Africa. The sediment thickness indicator

map (Figure 8, lower left) shows the areas with sufficient sedimentary thickness. These locations generally correspond to the larger basins of Africa whereas the smaller basins are generally absent from this map.

Figure 8: Basin independent indicator maps. Upper left: geothermal gradient, upper right: sediment age, lower left: sediment thickness.

Figure 9 shows the hydrocarbon presence (upper left), the reservoir presence (upper right) and the maximum and minimum porosity class indicator maps (lower left and right respectively), for the BGS basin model. The hydrocarbon map shows that the majority of the medium and large basins of Africa host proven hydrocarbon systems. Notably absent are the lake/rift basin of Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, Tanzania, Malawi and Zambia. In the reservoir presence indicator map, larger continental basins as Tauodeni, Illumedden, Kalahari and Okavango appear to not have data that indicate the presence of a reservoir. Again, many of the smaller basins are also absent. The porosity indicator maps show even less data points of compared to the previous indicator maps. Notable absent are again the larger basins of Illumedden, Okavango and Kalahari. The Chad basin is not included in the BGS dataset and therefore does not show in this indicator map. Other indicator maps do shows data from the Chad basin (Appendix E). Something to note is the significantly lower maximum porosity indicator value in the Karoo and Abay basins.

Figure 9: Four BGS indicator maps: the hydrocarbon presence (upper left), the reservoir presence (upper right) and the maximum and minimum porosity class indicator maps (lower left and right respectively).

Figure 10 shows the maximum and minimum porosity (left and right respectively) burial anomaly indicator maps for both the clay poor and the clay rich sandstone (upper and lower respectively), of the BGS basin model. Comparing the clay rich and the clay poor sandstone, we can observe that both burial anomalies are nearly identical. Note that the apparent difference between the minimal burial anomaly indicator value maps is due to the difference in range of indicator values. We also observe the consistently lower value for the burial anomaly in the Karoo basin over all four plots. Additionally, we can observe that the basins in north Africa (Algeria, Tunisia, Libya) and basins of the eastern-central rift system (e.g. Muglad, Melut, White Nile, Anza) and Mozambique coastal have negative burial anomaly values.

The other three indicator maps related to basin models generally show similar trends as described above. Again, apparent differences are generally caused by a differing range of indicator values.

Figure 10: Four BGS indicator maps: the maximum and minimum porosity (left and right respectively) burial anomaly indicator maps for both the clay poor and the clay rich sandstone (upper and lower respectively).

Combined Indicator

Figure 11-14 show the combined indicator maps for the BGS, Evenick, Robertson and GETECH basin models for the clay poor (left) and clay rich (right) sandstone with the maximum (upper) and minimum (lower) porosity related indicators, respectively. We can observe that there is only a very small difference between the clay rich and clay poor indicator maps for the four basin models. All maximum indicator map values range between 2 and 23 whereas the minimum models range between 2 and 20 or 21. Generally speaking, all basin models indicate similar areas with low and high indicator values. However, there are differences between the scale and geometry of these high and low value areas. Both the BGS and the GETECH models and the Evenick and Robertson models show large similarities in terms of scale geometry of these high and low value zones. Overall, in all maximum basin models, we observe the highest indicator values in the Zaire basin, basins in northern Africa, basins in the Central African rift-zone, Angola basin, basins in Somalia, both Nile and Niger delta basins, Senegal-Mauritania basin, Mozambique Coastal basin, Morondava basin and the edges of the red sea basin. In the Evenick and Robertson indicator maps, the Upper Egypt and western Desert basins are also high scoring areas. However, these areas score lower in the BGS and GETECH models. The minimum porosity indicator maps also show the aforementioned areas as the highest scoring locations, but all values are all slightly reduced compared to the maximum porosity indicator maps.

Figure 11: BGS combined indicator maps for the maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 12: Evenick combined indicator maps for the maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 13: Roberston CGG combined indicator maps for the maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 14: GETECH combined indicator maps for the maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Geothermal Potential Map

Figures 15- 18 show the geothermal potential maps of the BGS, Evenick, Robertson, GETECH basin models for the clay poor (left) and clay rich (right) sandstone with the maximum (upper) and Minimum (lower) porosity related indicators, respectively. Here, indicator value 0 (dark blue) corresponds to the verdict “not favourable”, 1 (cyan) to “slightly favourable”, 2 (yellow/orange) to “favourable” and 3 (dark red) to “very favourable”. The highest scoring areas as mentioned in the previous section are also the areas with the most favourable geothermal potential. Notable additions are the areas with “favourable” geothermal potential. These areas include the Taoudeni, Chad, Kufra, Zambia Coastal, Gabon, Kwanza, Essaouira and Doukkala basins.

Figure 15: BGS geothermal potential maps based on maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 16: Evenick geothermal potential maps based on maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 17: Robertson CGG geothermal potential maps based on maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

Figure 18: GETECH geothermal potential maps based on maximum and minimum (top and bottom respectively) porosity related indicator values of clay poor (cp) and clay rich (cr) sandstone.

6. Discussion

Data availability

As stated before, the quality, quantity and extent of all data in the database varies significantly. This is also the main reason why we choose to perform an indicator-based analysis instead of a numerical-based analysis. However, some basins that are studied in more detail, for example the Abu Gharadig basin (Elmasry et al. (2022)), appear to have sufficient data to perform a numerical analysis on.

The extent and distribution of geothermal/reservoir related data is generally controlled by data from the hydrocarbon/petroleum industry. The basins that are deemed important by this industry, tend to be researched more extensively than the basins that are not of economic interest (i.e., no or insufficient hydrocarbons present). The most telling example is comparing the amount of research on one of the smaller Algerian basins compared to the much larger basins (in surface area) Tauodeni, Zaire or Angola (onshore) basin. Access to existing hydrocarbon research data is generally worsened by the colonial history of the different countries in Africa, as the former French colonies almost exclusively published in French during this period. This language barrier is likely to complicate searching and reading for basin related publications about said locations.

Adding to the problem of data availability is the amount of data which is likely available behind closed doors of either private hydrocarbon companies or governmental institutions. It is therefore reasonable to assume that a (substantial) portion of all relevant data is not publicly available. Reservoir characteristics are generally locked behind closed publications whereas other types of data as for example high resolution digital depth to basement maps are locked behind private companies (Exploration Fabric of Africa and Getech).

Porosity and burial

The porosity/permeability measurements come in a variety of different type and qualities, both in terms of how much detail the data contains and in terms of which type of porosity is measured. The conclusion would be that not all porosity/permeability data is equal in value, which therefore could be indicated in terms of a confidence rating. Note that due to limited time this version does not yet include these confidence ratios for the different indicators. However, direct effective porosity measurements would be rated the highest whereas indirect “non-differentiated” measurements would be rated the lowest

If we compare all porosity depth data to the porosity-depth curves from Figure 7 we can observe some anomalous measurements. The data in question are the maximum porosity measurements that far exceed the porosity-depth curve and exceed the +80% porosity mark. These values are hard to explain as most values far exceed even the surface porosity value by a large amount. This would essentially mean these rocks are even more porous at depth than sandstones that recently underwent diagenesis at the surface, which is very unlikely.

It is important to note that the deviation from the porosity-depth curve could also be related to a difference in lithology. Porosity-depth curves for different lithologies, as illustrated by the model of Limberger et al. (2017), are generally different in geometry but not to the extent that these lithologies could explain the extreme outliers as mentioned above. In this project we choose to ignore the effect of a reservoir with a different lithology, but this is compensated by the large thresholds of -50 and -80 percent that need to be reached before a porosity measurement would be affected by a burial anomaly.

Geothermal potential

As described in Chapter 5 and presented in Figures 15-18, basins with favourable geothermal potential include the basins in northern Africa, basins in the Central African rift-zone, basins in Somalia, the Zaire basin, Angola basin, both Nile and Niger delta basins, Senegal-Mauritania basin, Mozambique Coastal basin, Morondava basin, the Upper Egypt basin, western Desert basin, the

Tauodeni basin, Chad basin, Kufra basin, Zambia Coastal basin, Gabon basin, Kwanza basin, Essaouira basin, Doukkala basin and the edges of the red sea basin. Other locations that are deemed “not favourable” or “slightly favourable” are generally areas where there is either little to no sedimentary thickness or little to no data. The fact that the absence of data could be the basis of an unfavourable geothermal potential verdict, does mean that these areas are unfit for geothermal energy exploitation.

Note that the oceanic basins from the basin models are excluded from this analysis, but that marine passive margin basins are included. This is because geothermal energy exploitation for direct use is generally more favourable close to the market where it can be used. This is because if warm water/heat is transported over long distances, the heat has more time to dissipate before it can be used compared to geothermal systems that are located close to the intended market. Additionally, the extra cost that are associated with geothermal exploitation offshore compared to onshore/nearshore are significant enough to dissuade offshore geothermal energy exploitation.

For these reasons, the onshore and nearshore parts of a passive margin basin are assumed to be the only part of the basin that could be considered for geothermal potential exploitation. This makes the data from passive margins somewhat problematic as most of the passive margin basin is located offshore and consequently a large volume of the basin is located offshore as well. This makes reliably using the porosity measurements from the offshore part of a passive margin basin difficult. This problem however is largely ignored.

Basin data from the Arabian Peninsula are not included in this analysis and therefore the geothermal potential verdict of these areas should be ignored.

The results of this analysis are meant to illustrate potential targets for future geothermal potential research and data acquisition and the results should not be taken at face-value as a definitive statement on areas where geothermal energy is or is not feasible.

[Comparison with previous estimates of geothermal potential in Africa](#)

If we compare our work with the generalized geothermal potential map of Limberger et al. (2018) (Figure 19), we can observe both similarities and large differences between the geothermal potential maps. Both Limberger et al. (2018) and our results show high geothermal potential in parts of NW-Africa (particularly the basins of Algeria), the Muglad, the Melut and the Morondava basins, the north-eastern part of the Zaire basin and the coastal areas of Somalia, Mozambique and Tanzania. High potential areas which are missing from the results of Limberger et al. (2018) include large parts of the central African rift zone basins, Egypt, the sides of the red Sea basin, Senegal-Mauritania coastal areas, the Niger and Nile deltas and the Congo and Kwanza basins.

We can also observe that the areas of high potential are significantly smaller in the results of Limberger et al. (2018), compared to our results. The relatively large differences between the areas of high potential could perhaps be explained by the dependency of our model on the basin geometry models on which we projected the geothermal potential data. Except for the basin model of BGS, all basin models show relatively large basin geometries. This causes our potential maps to show larger potential areas compared to the results of Limberger et al. (2018). The absence of high potential areas in the results of Limberger et al. (2018) is likely caused by the absence of reservoir specific characteristics in their study.

Comparing our continental scale results with smaller regional studies will be difficult due to the relatively low resolution of our results. These local studies generally focus on lateral variations in a specific basin. Determining these lateral variations within a basin in our results is generally not very reliable given that most of the indicators that we used are assigned to one specific basin as a constant.

Figure 19: Generalized indicator map from Limberger et al. (2018) showing locations suitable for all direct-use geothermal applications combined.

Limitations of this analysis

This analysis is completely based on published geoscientific literature. Socio-economic factors (e.g. population density, distance between source and market) are not considered in this analysis.

This study does not include data from the Arabian Peninsula or oceanic basins. Also note that basin characteristics measurements obtained from the offshore part of a passive margin basin are assumed to also be applicable for the onshore part of the basin.

The limited amount of data and the inhomogeneous data distributions over the continent required us to make simplifications about the geometry of reservoirs. We implicitly assume that a certain reservoir thickness and other reservoir related data is uniform for a particular basin. We thus not considered lateral variations in basin characteristics, except for the grid-based data (e.g. sedimentary thickness, geothermal gradient).

We also assumed that porosity measurements from one basin can be translated to another basin using the nomenclature link tables. This inherently assumes that reservoirs located in one basin are also present in the neighbouring or overarching basins. While there is data that suggests that reservoirs with a similar name and composition are present in some neighbouring basins, as for example the reservoirs such as the Adigrat sandstone (Quiroga et al. (2022)), the Bahariya sandstone (Elhossainy et al. (2021)) or the Abu Roash formation (Zahran et al. (2011), Bekhiet et al. (2011)). However, this is not necessarily proven for all basins.

The database input data of the indicator maps is very reliant on the basin geometry models. Choosing different basin shape models can result in an increase or decrease of the surface area that is considered to have a good geothermal potential.

An assumption regarding the burial anomaly is that we assumed that all clastic reservoirs are inherently sandstones with some clay components. We thus ignored lithological variation in reservoirs and assumed that fluids generally flow in the direction of least pressure resistance which in a mixed reservoir is the sandstone part. Additionally, carbonate reservoirs contribute to a smaller percentage of the result than clastic reservoirs. While there are sound reasons to exclude these reservoirs from the porosity related indicators, based on the data used in this study alone, there is not necessarily a reason to conclude that clastic reservoirs are better than carbonate reservoirs in terms of geothermal energy.

It is also important to note the limited resolution of certain data (particularly the sedimentary thickness grid of Laske & Masters (2013)). This means that smaller basins are not well represented in terms of sedimentary thickness. This is apparent in the indicator maps that rely on this input data.

Also, we chose indicators that can be linked directly or indirectly to geothermal energy. Some are arguably stronger than others (geothermal gradient and porosity versus basin age). We tried to reflect this in the indicator values. Including more indicators as for example groundwater system locations or altering the indicator values, could influence the results.

Finally, it is important to note that the indicator values are chosen somewhat arbitrary. This is not to say that the results are not valid, but it is important to consider that a location with a value of 12 is not two times better than a location with a value of 6. These indicators represent relative differences, not absolute differences.

Suggestions for future work

Limited time of this internship and the quality, quantity and extend of the data has limited us in the analysis. We therefore would like to suggest future research opportunities to improve and refine the results in this project.

First, it is important to note that adding/including more indicators that can be related to geothermal energy exploration could improve the results, these could include parameters that include tectonic stability, groundwater systems and parameters that could evaluate carbonate reservoirs.

The results overall could benefit from more lithological information, first in terms of the incomplete "lithology and well column" section of the database and secondly in terms of the reservoir lithology as mentioned previously.

Initially we planned on performing numerical calculations on selected basins that contain sufficient amounts and quality data. This proved difficult for most basin because of the limited amount of data available. However, a quantitative assessment of geothermal potential in terms of energy or monetary value would be very valuable for the GAA project as a whole. Note that some basins in the northern part of Africa (Algeria and Egypt), are generally well studied and could potentially be assessed quantitatively with the current data.

To perform such calculations for basins in Africa without much data, more data is required. This can be realized by acquiring/collecting more data or by introducing more partners to the project as for example the Exploration Fabric of Africa, GETECH or other hydrocarbon companies. The latter option should be considered before considering the prior option to reduce redundant workloads.

7. Conclusion

A literature study and an indicator analysis allowed us to create a reservoir characteristics and basin information database that in turn was used to create geothermal potential maps to determine locations for potential future geothermal energy exploration. These deliverables will all be made digitally accessible in the Geothermal Atlas of Africa.

Basins with favourable geothermal potential include the basins in northern Africa, basins in the Central African rift-zone, basins in Somalia, the Zaire basin, Angola basin, both Nile and Niger delta basins, Senegal-Mauritania basin, Mozambique Coastal basin, Morondava basin, the Upper Egypt basin, western Desert basin, the Tauodeni basin, Chad basin, Kufra basin, Zambia Coastal basin, Gabon basin, Kwanza basin, Essaouira basin, Doukkala basin and the edges of the red sea basin.

This study provides a start to a continental scale geoscientific database in the strongly fragmented continent of Africa (in terms of geoscience data). This research should be used as a steppingstone for both future geothermal potential energy exploration and could be used for creating a continental scale geoscientific database of Africa.

However, note that much work still needs to be done to more clearly map the geothermal potential and to create an open-source geoscientific database for the African continent. Both could significantly improve by the acquisition of new data and new partners to the GAA project.

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Appendices

A

- Complete excel database (Files)

B

- Complete QGIS project (File)

C

- Complete PyCharm code (Files)

D

- Input and output files required for the indicator analysis (Files)

E

- All individual indicator maps

Note: Appendices A, B, C and D are not included in this report. Please contact the UU supervisor (fred.beekman@uu.nl) to get access to these files.

Grid-Based

BGS

EVE

ROB

GET

F

- All Combined indicator maps

BGS

EVE

ROB

GET

**Utrecht
University**

TNO innovation
for life

G

- All Geothermal potential maps

BGS

EVE

ROB

GET

